

**ENERGY INSPECTION OF ELECTRICAL EQUIPMENT OF THE
MECHANICAL SHOP OF THE JOINT VENTURE JOINT STOCK
COMPANY “UZELEKTROAPPARAT-ELECTROSHIELD”**

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By energy audit, we mean a survey of enterprises, organizations, and individual industries undertaken at their initiative to determine opportunities for saving energy consumption. This helps the enterprise implement savings in practice by introducing energy efficiency mechanisms, as well as aiming to introduce an energy management system at the enterprise. The object of an energy audit can be any enterprise, energy installation, building, or unit that consumes or produces energy.

The final document of the energy audit is a report that contains the results of a study on the state of energy and energy consumption at the facility, a description of the facility, and recommendations for efficient energy consumption.

This article discusses the issues related to the energy survey, i.e., the energy audit of the mechanical shop of JSC 'Uzelektroapparat-electroshield'.

The production activity of the mechanical shop (hereinafter referred to as MS) involves the manufacturing of metal parts and components for the main products of the plant. The MS serves as the main production facility where metalworking machines are located.

All conductive parts of electrical installations, networks, and other electricity consumers underwent examination. Particular attention was given to places and areas

with increased heating on electrical connections (bolts, screws), contacts (moving, fixed), fuse sockets, and areas of electrical connections of cables and wires.

During the instrumental examination using an infrared thermometer, appropriate measurements were taken to determine places (points) with unacceptably high temperatures (above 65°C) of conductive surfaces.

According to the measurement results, no places with excessive thermal overheating were recorded, except for electrical contacts on the jaws of fuse groups, which often exceeded a temperature of more than 50°C.

The measurement results are presented only for those installations for which deviations of power quality parameters from their optimal and satisfactory values were detected and recorded. This will allow us to further group the observed deviations and assess the impact of these deviations on the energy efficiency of the operation of a specific group of electrical installations and/or equipment.

Further, the results of instrumental measurements will be presented in the following sequence (without indicating numbers):

Indicating the type of electrical installation (equipment), numbers of switchboards to which groups of electricity consumers are fed, places of connection of measuring instruments, etc.;

A graph is provided indicating the parameter (indicator) that was measured;

This is followed by an analysis of the results obtained with a description of the identified shortcomings and violations;

A table will be presented, summarizing the values of all measured parameters for electrical installations that have deviations in the values of power consumption quality parameters;

Based on the results of instrumental measurements for the MS and independent production site, a summary table will be presented indicating the identified deficiencies and a description of the losses and damages that these deviations lead to.

For the energy survey, all measurements were carried out using an AR-5 device. An examination and analysis of electrical parameters in the power supply network,

powered from electrical power cabinet “PS №1” (four metalworking machines and two units of cranes are powered) were carried out. When carrying out measurements with the AR-5 device, three metalworking machines were in normal operation mode, which also operated in the mode of alternating their joint and/or single use. When measuring electrical parameters in the power supply network, factors worthy of attention were identified, such as the presence of current imbalance, multiple currents at starting torques, frequent “surges,” and “sags” of load currents.

Fig 1. Load current graph.

The structure of the curves on the resulting graphs characterizes the alternation of operating modes of the machines. Initially, two machines were in operation, followed by the simultaneous activation of three machines. The current load was periodically switched off, with one machine unit being turned on intermittently.

Fig.2. Network power factor graph.

During measurements, a rather low power factor value was recorded in the consumer network, in the operating mode range, ranging from 0.15 to 0.52 (not taking into account starting torques). Such a low power factor indicates a significant lack of reactive power compensation in the plant-wide power supply network.

Fig.3. Network harmonic diagram.

During the measurements, harmonics were recorded in the operating current network of consumers, resulting in the distortion of the sinusoidal curve of the fundamental frequency. The generalized data of the measurement results for the main electrical parameters in the power supply network for electricity consumers of cabinet 'PS №1' are summarized in the following table:

Measured parameters	Unit	Nominal value	According to instrumental measurements	Note
Voltage	Volt	400	399	Fine
Current	Ampere	-	4 ÷ 36	Depending on load conditions
Frequency	Hz	50	50	Fine

Power factor	-	0,86	0,14 ÷ 0,73	Required to install KRM
Active power	kW	-	1 ÷ 12	Depending on changes in load currents
Reactive power	kvar	-	4 ÷ 19	Depending on the power factor in the network
Full power	kVA	-	2 ÷ 24	Depending on load conditions
Current harmonics	%	10 - 12	36,3 ÷ 43	It is recommended to install harmonic filters
Voltage harmonics	%	2 - 5	1,8 ÷ 2	Fine
Active energy (during the measurement period)	kWh	0,001		
Reactive energy (per measurement period)	kvar*h	2		
Measurement period	Minutes, seconds	9 minutes and 51 seconds		
Active energy consumption (per hour)	kWh	0,0061		
Reactive energy consumption (per hour)	kvar*h	12,183		

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